

Axonal mapping of motor and sensory components within the ulnar nerve and its branches

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36

37 **Abstract**

38 **Objectives:** Intrinsic function is indispensable for dexterous hand movements. Distal ulnar nerve
39 defects can result in intrinsic muscle dysfunction and sensory deficits. Although the ulnar nerve's
40 fascicular anatomy has been extensively studied, quantitative and topographic data on motor axons
41 traveling within this nerve remains elusive.

42 **Methods:** The ulnar nerves of 14 heart-beating organ donors were evaluated. The motor branches to
43 the flexor carpi ulnaris (FCU) and flexor digitorum profundus (FDP) muscles, the dorsal branch
44 (DoBUN) as well as three segments of the ulnar nerve were harvested in two-centimeter increments.
45 Samples were subjected to double immunofluorescence staining using antibodies against choline-
46 acetyltransferase and neurofilament.

47 **Results:** Samples revealed over 25,000 axons in the ulnar nerve at the forearm level, with a motor
48 axon proportion of only 5%. The SBUN and DoBUN show high axon numbers of over 21,000 and
49 9,300, respectively. The axonal mapping of over 1,300 motor axons revealed an increasing
50 motor:sensory ratio from proximal ulnar nerve (1:20) to the deep branch of the ulnar nerve (1:7). The
51 motor branches (FDP and FCU) show that sensory axons outnumber motor axons by a ratio of 10:1.

52 **Conclusions:** Knowledge of the detailed axonal architecture of motor and sensory components of the
53 human ulnar nerve is of utmost importance for surgeons considering fascicular grafting or nerve
54 transfer surgery. The low number of efferent axons in motor branches of the ulnar nerve and their
55 distinct topographical distribution along the distal course of this particular nerve make this
56 information indispensable for modern nerve surgery.

57

58 **Main Text**

59 **1 Introduction**

60 Nerve injuries are among the most debilitating neuropathic disorders, which affect otherwise healthy
61 young patients^{1,2}. Traumatic injury of the ulnar nerve may result in severe impairment of motor
62 function, dysesthesia, and pain in the lesioned hand³. A surgical intervention is often needed to
63 restore motor and/or sensory hand function in the most acute traumatic injuries. One of the surgical
64 procedures are nerve transfers, whereby branches of uninjured nerves are rewired to injured ulnar
65 nerve branches^{4,5}. Successful muscle reinnervation is achieved only when the donor nerve axons are
66 correctly wired to the appropriate targets.^{6,7}

67 The ulnar nerve is responsible for ulnar adduction, finger flexion (Digg. IV and V), intrinsic hand
68 function as well as sensory innervation of the forearm and ulnar side of the hand. It is divided into a
69 superficial and deep branch at wrist level, which provide sensory and motor innervation of the hand,
70 respectively⁸. Due to the increasing feasibility of nerve transfer procedures, various studies
71 investigated overall axon counts as well as fascicular distributions in ulnar nerve branches⁹⁻¹¹.
72 However, the distinctive (motor and sensory) axonal composition of these branches remains scarcely
73 explored, which is due to the lack of specific molecular markers to distinguish between different
74 neuronal types (i.e., somatic efferent vs. visceral afferent)¹². A recent study unveiled that sensory
75 components of forearm nerves outnumber motor axons by a ratio of 9:1¹³. Consequently, a distinctive
76 axonal mapping is missing to provide an accurate blueprint of the axonal distribution within the ulnar
77 nerve and its branches.

78 In this study, we performed a double immunofluorescence staining of the ulnar nerve and its
79 branches (deep, superficial and dorsal branches [DBUN, SBUN and DoBUN respectively]; flexor
80 carpi ulnaris [FCU] and flexor digitorum profundus [FDP] branches). Sensory and motor components
81 of each nerve branch were quantified. Moreover, the intraneural distribution of motor fascicles in the
82 distal ulnar nerve was analyzed.

83 **2 Materials and methods**

84 **2.1 Sample harvesting and fixation**

85 Fourteen heart-beating human organ donors were used in this study. The ulnar nerve was dissected
86 bilaterally using a standardized approach¹⁴. Samples were harvested in 14 heart beating organ donors
87 immediately after organ procurement and no longer than 12 hours postmortem to prevent enzyme
88 decay (choline-acetyltransferase [ChAT]). First, the bifurcation of the ulnar nerve's main trunk into
89 the superficial [SBUN] and deep [DBUN] branches was identified in Guyon's canal. Afterwards, the
90 ulnar nerve was exposed up until the medial epicondyle (Figure 1) and then followed proximal from
91 the dorsal branch's branching point towards the medial epicondyle to expose the FCU's and FDP's
92 motor branches. The longest branches to the FDP and FCU were harvested for axon quantification.
93 After harvesting the motor branches, the SBUN and DBUN were dissected bluntly using optical
94 magnification until two branches were distinguishable. After the nerve branches were separated, two-
95 centimeter segments of both the SBUN and DBUN were harvested. Multiple ulnar nerve specimens
96 were harvested proximal to the bifurcation in two-centimeter intervals: main trunk distal to proximal
97 [MT1, MT2 and MT3]. The last segment [MT4] was harvested two centimeters proximal to the
98 branching point of the dorsal branch [DoBUN]. Approval was obtained from the ethics committee of
99 the Medical University of Vienna (reference number EK Nr: 1213/2012).

100 The harvested samples were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 24 hours immediately after
101 harvesting, followed by immersion in 0.1M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) for the next 24 hours at
102 +4° Celsius. The samples were dehydrated using increasing sucrose concentrations (10, 25, and 40%
103 in PBS) for 24 hours each and then embedded in Tissue-Tek® O.C.T. Compound (Sakura Finetek
104 Europe B.V., Alphen aan den Rijn, Netherlands). The nerve samples were cut into 10µm thick
105 sections using a Cryotom (Leica CM3050 Cryostat, Leica Biosystems, Germany) and mounted on
106 Superfrost Ultra Plus® microscope slides (Thermo Scientific/Menzel).

107 **2.2 Immunofluorescence labeling**

108 The harvested samples underwent double immunofluorescence staining using the following neuronal
109 markers: chicken anti-neurofilament (anti-NF, RRID number AB_177520, 1:2000), goat anti-choline
110 acetyltransferase (anti-ChAT, RRID number AB_2079751, 1:100). Anti-NF is a pan-neuronal
111 marker, whereas anti-ChAT visualizes cholinergic axons^{13,15}. Secondary antibodies used in this study
112 were conjugated with Alexa fluor 488 or 568, obtained from Thermo Fisher (Waltham, MA, USA)
113 and used at a concentration of 1:500.

114 Before antibody application, the tissue was blocked with 10% normal rabbit serum for one hour.
115 Then, the tissue was incubated with the primary antibodies diluted in 0.1M PBS containing 0.1%
116 Triton X-100 (PBS-T) for 48 hours at +4° Celsius. Following extensive washing in PBS-T, the tissue
117 was incubated with the secondary antibodies for two hours at room temperature. Finally, the tissue
118 was rinsed again and mounted using Fluorescent Mounting Medium from Dako (S3023). A more
119 detailed description of immunolabeling is provided by Gesslbauer et al.¹³.

120 **2.3 Confocal and fluorescence imaging**

121 Fluorescence labeled specimens were analyzed either with a TissueFax (TissueFAXS;
122 TissueGnostics, Vienna, Austria) slide scanner or with a confocal laser scanning microscope [CLSM
123 (Olympus FV3000, Olympus Europa SE & Co. KG, Hamburg, Germany)]. A series of virtual CLSM
124 sections between 1 and 2 µm thickness were cut through the structures of interest. Each section was
125 photo-documented with a 1024x1024 pixel resolution and 3D projections were rendered using Image
126 J software (NIH, Bethesda, MA, USA). Double-colored images were generated using lasers with
127 excitation wavelengths of 488 and 568 nm. A semi-automated algorithm integrated in the software
128 StrataQuest (version 5.1.249) and TissueQuest (version 4.0.1.0128) (TissueGnostics) was used for
129 axon quantification, as previously described¹³.

130 **2.4 Statistical analysis**

131 Normal distribution was tested using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Descriptive statistics were used for
132 all nerve samples. Parametric data is presented as absolute and relative values or as mean and
133 standard deviation. Nonparametric values including categorical values are expressed as median with
134 interquartile range (IQR).

135

136 **3 Results**

137 **3.1 Axonal components of the distal ulnar nerve branches**

138 The main trunk of the ulnar nerve as well as the distal branches [DBUN, SBUN and DoBUN] show a
139 polyfascicular architecture (Figure 1). The ulnar nerve (proximal to the DoBUN) has an overall axon

140 number of 26,900 (5,000), of which 1,300 (300) are motor nerve fibers. The DoBUN has a variable
141 overall axon count of approximately 9,300 (range 4,244-13,240) (Table 1). The overall axon count
142 for the SBUN is 21,400 (3,400) and most axons are ChAT-negative, indicating their afferent nature
143 (Figure 2, 3). The number of motor axons in the SBUN is 51 (6.4), which are responsible for the
144 motor control of the palmaris brevis muscle. The most distal motor branch of the ulnar nerve, the
145 DBUN, has a mixed axonal composition (Figure 2). Its overall axon number is 8,900 (1,400), of
146 which 1,200 (280) are efferent (Table 1). The quantification indicates that only around 14% of the
147 total neuronal population in the “motor” deep branch of the ulnar nerve actually contributes to the
148 motor control of the intrinsic muscles.

149 **3.2 Intraneural fascicular topography of the deep branch of the ulnar nerve**

150 The motor fascicles of the DBUN and the distal main trunk of the ulnar nerve were identified
151 according to ChAT-positive signals. The overall axon numbers in fascicles containing ChAT-positive
152 signals (motor fascicles of the DBUN) were quantified from distal to proximal along the main trunk
153 of the ulnar nerve up to the DoBUN (Figure 2, 3). The overall axon numbers within motor fascicles
154 are: DBUN 8,900 (1,400), MT1 10,300 (2,500), MT2 11,000 (3,500) and MT3 12,200 (3,000). The
155 motor axon numbers are: DBUN 1,200 (280), MT1 1,350 (450), MT2 1,350 (420) and MT3 1,250
156 (320). These results indicate constant counts within the motor fascicles of the ulnar nerve with a
157 slight decrease of the sensory components towards the distal emergence of the DBUN (Figure 4).
158 Thus, the ratio of motor axons to overall axon number increases from proximal to distal: for MT3 11
159 (4.6)%, for MT2 12.5 (4.5)%, for MT1 13.6 (4.2)% and for DBUN 14.3 (5.3)% (Figure 3). The
160 number of motor fascicles varied from distal to proximal: for DBUN 6.5 (IQR 6-9.5), for MT1 8.5
161 (IQR 7.3-10.5), for MT2 6.5 (IQR 4.8-9.5) and for MT3 6 (IQR 6-6.8) (Figure 4).

162 **3.3 Mixed axonal composition of the ulnar motor branches**

163 Along with the DBUN, the proximal motor branches [FDP and FCU] of the ulnar nerve demonstrate
164 a mixed axonal composition (Figure 5). The FDP branch shows an overall axon count of 2,100 (370),
165 of which 190 (43) are motor nerve fibers. The FCU branch demonstrated an overall axon count of
166 1,400 (350), of which 140 (61) are motor nerve fibers (Figure 6). These findings indicate that only a
167 small motor unit number is needed for native motor control of the FCU and FDP muscles.

168 **4 Discussion**

169 The human hand is the most dexterous biological tool available to our disposal. Intrinsic and extrinsic
170 hand function is governed by the neuronal sources travelling via the ulnar, median and radial nerves
171 to these muscles. Damage to the ulnar nerve particularly results in severe intrinsic muscle
172 dysfunction and thus has deleterious effects on global hand function. Understanding the distribution
173 and topography of axonal population within the ulnar nerve is thus an essential prerequisite for a
174 successful surgical intervention after nerve injury. Here, we reveal the exact distribution of the over
175 25,000 axons of the ulnar nerve into its sensory and motor branches at the forearm level. The axonal
176 mapping of over 1,300 motor axons revealed an increasing motor:sensory ratio from the proximal
177 ulnar nerve (1:20) to its deep branch (1:7). The motor branches of the ulnar nerve (FCU, FDP)
178 showed only a share of 10% motor axons, indicating a low motor neuron number responsible for
179 neuromuscular control of forearm muscles.

180 Although the ulnar nerve has been intensively investigated due to its clinical importance, previous
181 studies mainly obtained the myelinated axon count or dimensional measurements^{9,16,17}. A large
182 discrepancy was observed when comparing myelinated axon counts with our total axon counts,

183 highlighting a high number of non-myelinated fibers in peripheral nerves¹⁸. Moreover, myelinated
 184 axon counts do not distinguish between motor or sensory axons, thus, providing only an
 185 approximation of the motor axon population. Distinguishing different axonal types is challenging due
 186 to the lack of specific molecular markers for different neuronal types¹². Recent studies utilized
 187 specific molecular markers to distinguish between motor, sympathetic or afferent axons^{13,19}. This
 188 technique allows for the quantitative analysis of motor and sensory axons via the cholinergic
 189 metabolism present in all motor fibers.²⁰

190 Modality matched reconstruction obviously is the single most important factor in nerve transfer
 191 surgery that influences outcomes by providing a sufficient amount of motor axons reaching their
 192 appropriate target muscles, while keeping the donor site morbidity as low as possible²¹. In 1997,
 193 Wang and Zhu described transferring the anterior interosseus nerve (AIN) of the median nerve to the
 194 DBUN to restore intrinsic hand function¹⁶. Schenck et al. analyzed the histomorphometry of the
 195 nerves associated with this nerve transfer and revealed that the AIN was significantly smaller in all
 196 histomorphometric measurements⁹. *Here, authors showed an overall of 1,800 motor axons in the*
 197 *DBUN which corresponds to the motor contribution of the ulnar nerve to the intrinsic hand function.*
 198 *Knowledge of the exact motor axons number of the DBUN can help surgeons to select the most*
 199 *appropriate donor nerve with the equivalent motor axon number to surgically restore function in low*
 200 *ulnar nerve injuries.*

201 Serial sections of the ulnar nerve in two-centimeter increments revealed that the ulnar nerve is
 202 arranged into groups of fascicles proximal to its division in Guyon's canal which distally become the
 203 DBUN and SBUN (Figure 1). However, this arrangement is not constant over the course of the
 204 forearm, as complex rearrangements of fascicles were observed proximal to the ulnar nerve's
 205 division. The finding of complex fascicular exchange is in accordance to the reports on the
 206 topography of the ulnar nerve by Sunderland in 1945 and has also been described in other nerves as
 207 well^{22,23}. This study outlines the topography of motor axons within the ulnar nerve's fascicles and
 208 shows a varying number of fascicles containing motor axons (6-9) at different levels of the ulnar
 209 nerve (Figure 1, 4). Furthermore, the share of motor axons in motor fascicles of the ulnar nerve
 210 gradually increased towards the DBUN, which might be explained by interfascicular interchange.
 211 *This higher motor axons ratio of the motor fascicles in the DBUN compared to the proximal main*
 212 *trunk of the ulnar nerve provides morphologic correlates that the most distal coaptation to the*
 213 *DBUN may achieve a more precise axonal regrowth towards the target muscles and subsequently a*
 214 *better clinical outcome.*

215 Advancements in microsurgery led to increasing feasibility of selective nerve transfers and knowing
 216 the anatomy and axon counts of the donor and recipient nerves are essential prerequisites. Previous
 217 reports demonstrated an overall axon count of 832 (218)¹⁸ or 872 (92)²⁶ in the FDP branch and 659
 218 (191)¹⁸, 372 (35)²⁷ or 743 (range 623-900)²⁸ in the FCU branch. The higher axon numbers in this
 219 study (2,100 for FDP and 1,400 for FCU) is due to the quantification of myelinated as well as non-
 220 myelinated axons. Moreover, our data distinguished for the first time the pure motor axon population
 221 (191 in FDP and 138 in FCU) in the motor branches of the ulnar nerve. *The knowledge of precise*
 222 *motor axon numbers in the FDP and FCU branches can facilitate the selection of donor or recipient*
 223 *branches for nerve transfer procedures. Since motor axons match between the donor and recipient*
 224 *nerves is crucial for postoperative outcomes, the dataset on the FDP and FCU branches can assist*
 225 *surgeons in preoperative decision-making for the selection of the most suitable donor/recipient nerve*
 226 *in diverse reconstruction scenarios*²⁹⁻³¹. *While the data on the ulnar nerve branches do not provide*
 227 *physicians with a complete spectrum of donor/recipient nerves available for nerve transfers, the*
 228 *authors of this study aim to create a comprehensive dataset on all peripheral nerve branches in the*

229 *upper extremity*. Moreover, these findings show that only a low number of motor units are needed for
230 natural neuromuscular control of these forearm muscles. This phenomenon grants insight into how
231 much of the neural input should be redirected to a denervated muscle for sufficient functional
232 recovery.

233 5 Limitations

234 While the data generated by immunofluorescence staining of nerve cross section provides high
235 quality data which describes the afferent or efferent nature of individual axons, curation of this data
236 highly depends on the presence of antigens in the harvested nerves. For this purpose, fresh organ
237 donor nerves were used in this study to achieve reproducible and reliable results. Limited availability
238 of organ donors during the COVID-19 pandemic and restricted access were responsible for the small
239 sample sizes, however, standard deviations were generally very small. While staining sequential
240 nerve samples is optimal for axon quantification, its use for studying the fascicular arrangements is
241 limited. To overcome this limitation, techniques including optical tissue clearing should be applied
242 for analysis of the continuous fascicular arrangement³².

243 6 Conclusions

244 The present study describes the topographical distribution of 26,900 (5,000) total axons in the ulnar
245 nerve at forearm level and mapped the path of 1,300 (300) motor nerve fibers over the course of the
246 forearm until the division into the DBUN and SBUN. A low number of efferent axons were revealed
247 in the motor branches. Detailed information about the axonal architecture of the human ulnar nerve
248 provides valuable information for surgeons considering fascicular grafting or nerve transfer surgery.

249 7 Author Contributions

250 V.T., U.M., L.A.H., and O.C.A.: conception and design. V.T., U.M., L.A.H., J.K., D.C.D., G.L.,
251 M.L., O.P., and O.C.A.: sample harvesting. V.T., U.M., R.B. and O.C.A.: imaging analysis. V.T.,
252 U.M., L.A.H., J.K., R.B., K.D.B., and O.C.A.: analyses and interpretation of data. R.B., K.D.B. and
253 O.C.A.: supervision. V.T., U.M., C.F., L.A.H., and O.C.A.: drafting of the article. All authors critical
254 revision and final approval of the version to be published.

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259 9 References

- 260 1. Taylor CA, Braza D, Rice JB, Dillingham T. The Incidence of Peripheral Nerve Injury in
261 Extremity Trauma. *American Journal of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation*. 2008;87(5):381-
262 385. doi:10.1097/PHM.0b013e31815e6370
- 263 2. Bergmeister KD, Große-Hartlage L, Daeschler SC, et al. Acute and long-term costs of 268
264 peripheral nerve injuries in the upper extremity. Simmen H-P, ed. *PLOS ONE*.
265 2020;15(4):e0229530. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0229530
- 266 3. Ruijs ACJ, Jaquet J-B, Kalmijn S, Giele H, Hovius SER. Median and Ulnar Nerve Injuries: A

- 267 Meta-Analysis of Predictors of Motor and Sensory Recovery after Modern Microsurgical
 268 Nerve Repair. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*. 2005;116(2):484-494.
 269 doi:10.1097/01.prs.0000172896.86594.07
- 270 4. Novak CB, Mackinnon SE. Distal Anterior Interosseous Nerve Transfer to the Deep Motor
 271 Branch of the Ulnar Nerve for Reconstruction of High Ulnar Nerve Injuries. *Journal of*
 272 *Reconstructive Microsurgery*. 2002;18(6):459-464. doi:10.1055/s-2002-33326
- 273 5. Sallam AA, El-Deeb MS, Imam MA. Nerve Transfer Versus Nerve Graft for Reconstruction
 274 of High Ulnar Nerve Injuries. *The Journal of Hand Surgery*. 2017;42(4):265-273.
 275 doi:10.1016/J.JHSA.2017.01.027
- 276 6. Cederna PS, Youssef MKH, Asato H, Urbanchek MG, Kuzon WM. Skeletal muscle
 277 reinnervation by reduced axonal numbers results in whole muscle force deficits. *Plastic and*
 278 *Reconstructive Surgery*. 2000;105(6):2003-2009. doi:10.1097/00006534-200005000-00014
- 279 7. Schreiber JJ, Byun DJ, Khair MM, Rosenblatt L, Lee SK, Wolfe SW. Optimal axon counts for
 280 brachial plexus nerve transfers to restore elbow flexion. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*.
 281 2015;135(1):135e-141e. doi:10.1097/PRS.0000000000000795
- 282 8. Polatsch DB, Melone CP, Beldner S, Incorvaia A. Ulnar Nerve Anatomy. *Hand Clinics*.
 283 2007;23(3):283-289. doi:10.1016/J.HCL.2007.05.001
- 284 9. Schenck TL, Stewart J, Lin S, Aichler M, Machens HG, Giunta RE. Anatomical and
 285 histomorphometric observations on the transfer of the anterior interosseous nerve to the deep
 286 branch of the ulnar nerve. *Journal of Hand Surgery: European Volume*. 2015;40(6):591-596.
 287 doi:10.1177/1753193414551909
- 288 10. Rui J, Zhou Y, Wang L, Li J, Gu Y, Lao J. Restoration of ulnar nerve motor function by
 289 pronator quadratus motor branch: an anatomical study. *Acta Neurochirurgica*.
 290 2016;158(4):755-759. doi:10.1007/s00701-016-2728-1
- 291 11. Chow JA, van Beek AL, Bilos ZJ, Meyer DL, Johnson MC. Anatomical basis for repair of
 292 ulnar and median nerves in the distal part of the forearm by group fascicular suture and nerve-
 293 grafting. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery - Series A*. 1986;68(2):273-280.
 294 doi:10.2106/00004623-198668020-00013
- 295 12. Zeng H, Sanes JR. Neuronal cell-type classification: Challenges, opportunities and the path
 296 forward. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*. 2017;18(9):530-546. doi:10.1038/nrn.2017.85
- 297 13. Gesslbauer B, Hruby LA, Roche AD, Farina D, Blumer R, Aszmann OC. Axonal components
 298 of nerves innervating the human arm. *Annals of Neurology*. 2017;82(3):396-408.
 299 doi:10.1002/ana.25018
- 300 14. Brown JM, Yee A, MacKinnon SE. Distal median to ulnar nerve transfers to restore ulnar
 301 motor and sensory function within the hand: Technical nuances. *Neurosurgery*.
 302 2009;65(5):966-977. doi:10.1227/01.NEU.0000358951.64043.73
- 303 15. Tereshenko V, Dotzauer DC, Maierhofer U, et al. Selective Denervation of the Facial
 304 Dermato-Muscular Complex in the Rat: Experimental Model and Anatomical Basis. *Frontiers*

- 305 *in Neuroanatomy*. 2021;15:15. doi:10.3389/fnana.2021.650761
- 306 16. Wang Y, Zhu S. Transfer of a branch of the anterior interosseus nerve to the motor branch of
307 the median nerve and ulnar nerve. *Chinese medical journal*. 1997;110(3):216-219.
- 308 17. Brill NA, Tyler DJ. Quantification of human upper extremity nerves and fascicular anatomy.
309 *Muscle & nerve*. 2017;56(3):463-471.
- 310 18. Cheah A, Lee EY, Lim AYT. Upper Extremity Axon Counts and Clinical Implications for
311 Motor Nerve Transfer. *Plastic and reconstructive surgery*. 2019;144(6):1044e-1050e.
312 doi:10.1097/PRS.00000000000006200
- 313 19. Tereshenko V, Maierhofer U, Dotzauer DC, et al. Newly identified axon types of the facial
314 nerve unveil supplemental neural pathways in the innervation of the face. *Journal of Advanced*
315 *Research*. April 2022. doi:10.1016/J.JARE.2022.04.009
- 316 20. Gruber H, Zenker W. Acetylcholinesterase: Histochemical differentiation between motor and
317 sensory nerve fibres. *Brain Research*. 1973;51(C):207-214. doi:10.1016/0006-8993(73)90373-
318 9
- 319 21. Mackinnon SE. Donor Distal, Recipient Proximal and Other Personal Perspectives on Nerve
320 Transfers. *Hand Clinics*. 2016;32(2):141-151. doi:10.1016/j.hcl.2015.12.003
- 321 22. Sunderland S. The intraneural topography of the radial, median and ulnar nerves. *Brain : a*
322 *journal of neurology*. 1945;68(4):243-298. doi:10.1093/BRAIN/68.4.243
- 323 23. Aszmann OC, Dellon AL. The internal topography of the axillary nerve: An anatomic and
324 histologic study as it relates to microsurgery. *Journal of Reconstructive Microsurgery*.
325 1996;12(6):359-363. doi:10.1055/s-2007-1006498
- 326 24. Leclercq C. General assessment of the upper limb. *Hand clinics*. 2003;19(4):557-564.
327 doi:10.1016/S0749-0712(03)00059-3
- 328 25. Hader M, Sporer ME, Roche AD, et al. Fascicular shifting: A novel technique to overcome
329 large nerve defects. *Journal of Neurosurgery: Spine*. 2017;27(6):723-731.
330 doi:10.3171/2017.3.SPINE16276
- 331 26. Üstün ME, Öğün TC, Büyükmumcu M, Salbacak A. Selective restoration of motor function in
332 the ulnar nerve by transfer of the anterior interosseous nerve: An anatomical feasibility study.
333 *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery - Series A*. 2001;83(4):549-552. doi:10.2106/00004623-
334 200104000-00009
- 335 27. Boutros S, Nath RK, Yüksel E, Weinfeld AB, Mackinnon SE. Transfer of flexor carpi ulnaris
336 branch of the ulnar nerve to the pronator teres nerve: Histomorphometric analysis. *Journal of*
337 *Reconstructive Microsurgery*. 1999;15(2):119-122. doi:10.1055/s-2007-1000081
- 338 28. Bertelli J, Soldado F, Ghizoni MF, Rodríguez-Baeza A. Transfer of a terminal motor branch
339 nerve to the flexor carpi ulnaris for triceps reinnervation: Anatomical study and clinical cases.
340 *Journal of Hand Surgery*. 2015;40(11):2229-2235. doi:10.1016/j.jhsa.2015.08.014

- 341 29. Bertelli JA, Soldado F, Rodríguez-Baeza A, Ghizoni MF. Transferring the Motor Branch of
342 the Opponens Pollicis to the Terminal Division of the Deep Branch of the Ulnar Nerve for
343 Pinch Reconstruction. *Journal of Hand Surgery*. 2019;44(1):9-17.
344 doi:10.1016/j.jhsa.2018.09.010
- 345 30. Arami A, Bertelli JA. Effectiveness of Distal Nerve Transfers for Claw Correction With
346 Proximal Ulnar Nerve Lesions. *Journal of Hand Surgery*. 2021;46(6):478-484.
347 doi:10.1016/j.jhsa.2020.10.015
- 348 31. Oberlin C, Béal D, Leechavengvongs S, Salon A, Dauge MC, Sarcy JJ. Nerve transfer to
349 biceps muscle using a part of ulnar nerve for C5-C6 avulsion of the brachial plexus:
350 Anatomical study and report of four cases. *Journal of Hand Surgery*. 1994;19(2):232-237.
351 doi:10.1016/0363-5023(94)90011-6
- 352 32. Daeschler SC, Zhang J, Phd TG, Borschel GH. Optical Tissue Clearing Enables Rapid, Precise
353 and Comprehensive Assessment of Three-Dimensional Morphology in Experimental Nerve
354 Regeneration Research. doi:10.1101/2021.01.28.428623
- 355
- 356

357 **10 Tables**

358 Table 1. Absolute axon quantification of motor and sensory components of the ulnar nerve.

359 ¹The MT4 segment is harvested proximal to the dorsal branch of the ulnar nerve.

360 ²The axonal quantification was performed only of the fascicles containing motor axons (ChAT⁺)
 361 within the main trunk of the ulnar nerve.

362 DBUN – deep branch of the ulnar nerve, SBUN – superficial branch of the ulnar nerve, DoBUN –
 363 dorsal branch of the ulnar nerve, MT1-4 – main trunk 1 - 4, FDP – flexor digitorum profundus, FCU
 364 – flexor carpi ulnaris, ChAT - choline-acetyltransferase.

	Overall axon number	Motor axon number (ChAT ⁺)	% of motor axons
Ulnar nerve (MT4) ¹	26,897 ± 4,966	1,329 ± 296	5.4 ± 1.7
DBUN	8,910 ± 1,417	1,203 ± 279	14.3 ± 5.3
SBUN	21,345 ± 3,401	51 ± 6.4	0.24 ± 0.08
DoBUN	9,306±4,411	n/a	n/a
Motor fascicle analysis ²			
MT1	10,270 ± 2,496	1,352 ± 447	13.6 ± 4.2
MT2	10,980 ± 3,501	1,346 ± 418	12.5 ± 4.5
MT3	12,169 ± 3,049	1,245 ± 320	11 ± 4.6
Motor branches of the ulnar nerve			
FDP	2,122 ± 374	191 ± 43	9.1 ± 1.9
FCU	1,430 ± 351	138 ± 61	9.6 ± 2.8

365

367

368 Figure 1. Fascicular and axonal distribution within the distal ulnar nerve. The main trunk of the ulnar
 369 nerve was harvested in segments (MT1-MT4) in two-centimeter increments. Cross-sections of
 370 corresponding ulnar nerve segments represent the distribution of motor (red and yellow axons) and
 371 sensory (exclusively red axons) fascicles within the distal ulnar nerve.

Ulnar nerve superficial branch

Ulnar nerve deep branch

Dorsal branch

372

373 Figure 2. Axonal mapping of motor (yellow) and sensory (red) axons in the deep, superficial, and
374 dorsal branches of the ulnar nerve.

375

376 Figure 3. Quantification of the ulnar nerve's motor and sensory axons. A. Overall axon number (red)
 377 of the motor fascicles within the ulnar nerve segments with corresponding motor axon number
 378 (green). B. Axon quantification of the SBUN, DoBUN and DBUN. *MT4 corresponds the ulnar
 379 nerve segment proximal to the DoBUN.

380

381 Figure 4. Motor axons distribution within the motor fascicles of the ulnar nerve. A. Share of motor
 382 axons within motor fascicles of the ulnar nerve. B. Number of fascicles in the ulnar nerve containing
 383 motor axons.

Flexor digitorum profundus

Flexor carpi ulnaris

384

385 Figure 5. Axonal topography of the motor branches to the flexor carpi ulnaris and flexor digitorum
386 profundus muscles. The cross-sections show a mixed axonal composition of motor (yellow) and
387 sensory (red) axons.

388

389

390 Figure 6. Axon quantification for the FDP's and FCU's branches.